

THE IMPORTANCE OF MARKETING IN FORMING THE INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *In this article, the production of goods and the development of sales problems, the changes that occur in the market quick adaptation, differentiated approach to consumers, competitive new creating goods and organizing their production, the market market research and forecasting and effective advertising considering the main goal of marketing to study development issues developed.*

Keywords: *marketing, market, environment, consumer, competition, country, economy, investment.*

Currently, the most effective and important way to develop the economy of any country and ensure its stability is attracting investments to the country's economy.

Investment is money spent to obtain economic results (profit, income) or to achieve a positive social result, deposits in banks, securities (shares, bonds), technologies, machines, equipment, licenses and results. any other wealth that gives 10.

It is known that increasing the efficiency of attracting investments depends on the level of the investment environment in the country. Investment attraction of investors is determined depending on how the investment environment is organized in the country. Marketing is of great importance in organizing the investment environment and effective use of attracted investments.

In countries with a developed market economy, investment activities are carried out in the following directions: individuals, citizens, non-state enterprises, economic associations, collective and partnership farms, organizations established on the basis of collective ownership and other legal entities. ; by organizations of administrative management and other administrative divisions of the government, state enterprises and institutions, by foreign individuals, private firms, associations, companies and other legal entities, and by other countries; jointly with local and foreign citizens, legal entities and the state.

Similarly, marketing activities should be organized, conducted and managed. On the basis of peace, tranquility, priority of law and economy in our country, implementation of adopted laws, favorable conditions are being created for conducting investment activities and developing market relations. The development of various forms of ownership, establishment of entrepreneurship and business, strengthening of foreign economic relations, increasing the role of joint ventures in the stabilization of the economy create the necessary opportunities for the full organization of investment activities. However, a lot of work needs to be done to manage marketing activities in this regard. These include,

includes marketing activities and activities aimed at clarifying the forms of organization of activities.

Organization of investment activities in a society with established market relations, its quantitative and qualitative expansion and development is aimed at reviving entrepreneurship, business and other activities for the purpose of making profit for individuals, legal entities and the state. Its main goal is to stabilize our economy, enter the world market, strengthen world-economic

relations and raise the standard of living of the population by organizing investment activities in the directions mentioned above. Marketing management activities in this regard, first of all, in the organization of investment activities, it should be directed to objects and subjects. Marketing research shows that the investment subjects mentioned above Individuals, legal entities and states with property and intellectual assets participating in investment activities in the rt direction. In conducting investment activities, its subjects are, on the one hand, the owners (investors) who have property and intellectual assets, and on the other hand, individuals, legal entities and the state that receive investors. Investment marketing should help the participants of this activity to choose the subject that can have the most effect on the country's economy, develop its scientifically based proposals and measures. In conducting investment activities, its subjects are, on the one hand, the owners (investors) who have property and intellectual assets, and on the other hand, individuals, legal entities and the state that receive investors. Investment marketing should help the participants of this activity to choose the subject that can have the most effect on the country's economy, develop its scientifically based proposals and measures. In conducting investment activities, its subjects are, on the one hand, the owners (investors) who have property and intellectual assets, and on the other hand, individuals, legal entities and the state that receive investors. Investment marketing should help the participants of this activity to choose the subject that can have the most effect on the country's economy, develop its scientifically based proposals and measures.

Marketing performs the following activities:

- Market research;
- Market sharing;
- Placement of goods;
- Implementation of marketing policy;
- Price policy;
- Distribution Policy;
- Transfer (forwarding) policy;
- Promotion, provision of additional services.

Forms of activation of economic relations that arise in the market, solving problems of production and sale of goods, quickly adapting to changes that occur in the market, a class approach to consumers, creating competitive new goods and organizing their production, studying the market situation and forecasting The main goal of marketing is to learn how to make and develop effective advertising.

Marketing is a type of activity related to the production and sale of goods and services aimed at satisfying the current and future needs of consumers. Marketing studies competition, consumer behavior modeling, product quality, competitiveness, customer incentives, advertising, and the market in depth.

The main goal of investors is to get a high level of income and efficiency from investment activities and to develop their own activities and market infrastructure

is to expand and change investment areas and objects accordingly. These things should not be overlooked by the marketer and he should actively participate in it. In this regard, they should work with the law of supply and demand depending on price changes, labor productivity growth, cost reduction and economic laws in general, considering all factors that determine investment. The main goal of the second party, that is, the subjects receiving investments, is to effectively use

the relations with investors, to achieve their goals in a short period of time in their chosen fields and, in turn, to achieve the development of production. Investment activity is connected with the areas chosen by the investor and the purposes for which investments should be spent, that is, with investment objects, and they differ depending on the areas of investment direction, participation in production, and spending activities. Marketers divide these objects into the following groups:

- Newly created and modernized capital funds and working capital in all sectors and sectors of the national economy;
- Scientific and technical products, research, supply, personnel training, retraining and their use;
- Ideological and general intellectual assets, copyrights, inventions, discovery rights, experience and the like, trust funds and securities, property rights and other property objects.

It is prohibited to direct investments for means that do not meet ecological and other standards, sanitary and hygienic requirements, are prohibited by decrees, laws and other legal documents, created and cannot be pursued, and these works cannot be the object of investment restrictions. It is forbidden to spend investments on citizens, legal entities and people who harm the legal rights and interests of the state.

Investors themselves have the right to choose sectors and sectors or several of them for directing and investing capital funds. Therefore, they conduct marketing research to do this. No one can force them in the choice of industry or investment objects. When choosing one or another field and investing in certain objects, investors make their own decisions based on the results of in-depth marketing research. Subjects of investment activity can be one investor or, if not, several participating investors engaged in business and other activities. The subjects of investment activities are investors, local and foreign citizens, legal entities, can be countries. Investments are carried out by the participants of the investment activity as executors of accepted orders or on the basis of the investor's assignment. Investors themselves calculate the size, areas and effectiveness of investments. Naturally, the services of marketing groups, departments or purely marketing enterprises are great in carrying out these works. In order to make investments, they involve individuals and legal entities on the basis of contracts of their own free will. Each country shall make decisions on the acquisition of investments, their use and the results of these activities on the basis of agreements, relying solely on its own laws, investors, they can also make decisions on transfer from other citizens and legal entities. In such cases, the investor's property is accepted as collateral for the obligation. Only the property that the borrower has the right to conduct a personal or full-time economy is taken as collateral. But in this case, the international laws and regulations adopted in the investor countries should not be ignored. Investors have the right to own, use, order and reinvest (convert to investment) investment results, investment objects. Pure marketing enterprises can act as a source, subject and object of investments. They do not invest their surplus funds in any of the above mentioned areas. can use it and not allow it to stand idle. It is inevitable that the income from this will be a source of additional development for the enterprise, increase in the well-being of employees. Many investors invest heavily in creating pure marketing ventures. In fact, the funds - investments directed for marketing will return to their owner with the highest profit. Therefore, this industry itself needs marketing research. funds allocated for marketing - investments return to their owner with the highest profit. Therefore, this industry itself needs marketing research. funds allocated for marketing - investments return to their owner with the highest profit. Therefore, this industry itself needs marketing research.

Currently, the importance of marketing in the development of economic sectors is increasing day by day. We can notice a positive increase in the income of enterprises that have correctly conducted marketing activities and the expansion of the enterprise's activities. This helps to achieve growth rates in the country's economy. Because now the enterprises that studied the market, distributed the goods correctly, placed the goods correctly, produced goods in accordance with the market demand and supply, and implemented the correct price policy, are achieving positive results and entering the world market. coming out with z products. It can be seen that organization of marketing activities is important in the development of the economy of every country. Efforts to achieve economic growth and ensure economic stability by making investments in the economy are being rapidly implemented in our country. We can see that this shows positive growth results in our economy. However, we can see that the marketing sector is relatively underdeveloped in our country. Marketing plays a big role in attracting investors to our country.

We offer the following suggestions for the development of marketing activities in our country: first, to carry out systematic work on the development of marketing in our country and thereby improve the investment environment in our country; secondly, applying world marketing experiences in our country and using them effectively; thirdly, increase the effectiveness of marketing research in the investment market; fourthly, to organize various "masterclass" classes with the participation of specialists and share experience with local industry representatives through this; fourthly, attracting experienced experts from abroad and sharing experience with them; fifth, to increase attention to marketing in enterprises.

In conclusion, the development of our economy now has an impact on every sector. Marketing is one of the most important areas, and it is of great importance in attracting investment to the country and improving the investment environment in the country. Marketing is an integral part of the investment environment and has a great impact on the development of the economy.

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